

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Ajayi****FIRST NAME: Babatunde****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 2016 on Windows 10

List your seven key concepts with page number range in the text

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism and Citations (EUCLID 2019, 2-12)
3. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-22)
4. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
5. Latin Abbreviations and Expression (EUCLID 2019, 56-59)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)
7. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)

UNDERSTANDING THE BASICS OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Starting the first course of this program, ACA-401D, and going through the provided materials, including a course pack and supporting videos, kicked off the beginning of a new writing experience. My previous writing encounters have sufficiently served me well in professional engagements such as communicating via e-mails, creating presentation slides, preparing business reports and official documents. In that regard, I expected that there would be a comparable difference between what I already know and what I will be learning taking this course. Bearing this in mind, I started by interacting with the coursepack, taking note of vital points needed to prepare this Response Paper (RP). EUCLID's academic standards emphasize proper academic writing. Understanding certain academic writing elements will set the paths to develop the thesis, research topics, analyze questions for quizzes, present results, et Cetera. The 14-minute video attached to the course served as a practical guide to fully grasp what the coursepack entails. This paper contains interaction with the above-listed concepts obtained from the coursepack. Also, it indicates the parts that may appear complicated, poorly explained, practical, controversial, et cetera.

2) FACTS AND EVIDENCE

The first chapter in the coursepack vividly talks about the basics of essay writing. As implied, essay writing aims to develop ideas that may be of interest to the readers. To achieve that, it has to be based on evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1). Academic writing typically discusses a topic or subject matter by giving the writer's opinion or report on the research that may have been conducted (Bailey 2011, 6). The research done is what provides the needed facts to base an essay. I believe that while writing academic essays, one must put out and away from any forms of emotion and feeling and must write in the most logical manner possible. This is not entirely applicable to many other forms of writing. In academic writing, a very vital feature is the presence of a good argument. A good argument is described as a "point of view presented concisely and logically, such that every stage of reasoning proves convincing enough to the readers" (Burnett 2008, 3). When structurally laid out, these arguments are practically just a direct way of communication with my instructors via writing, hence the need for them to be less opinionated and more factual.

The coursepack was able to identify the basic necessary steps through which an essay can be drafted. In writing an essay, it is important to define the question, analyze the task and understand what the essay requires. Doing this gives an avenue to establish and develop a point of view. It is then required to do researches about the research topic in order to garner enough facts to bridge the gap between the known and the unknown (EUCLID 2019, 2). I understand that it is essential to employ credible academic sources whose works appear essentially validated. It is advisable to access as many materials as possible, whether in a physical library or online, using different methods to conduct topic and subject searches (EUCLID 2019, 2).

An item instructed by the coursepack states to always maintain a balance while writing. The essay question is a critically important element to keep in mind while writing. This helps to maintain focus on the subject matter being argued (EUCLID 2019, 3). I agree that a focused mindset can help achieve a level of consistency in the logical information gathered. Equally, the essay's proper structure is as important as the thesis statement, which is meant to answer the essay question. Every paragraph sentence in an academic write-up has to lead up to a conclusion that supports the thesis statement. Hence, it is important to do away with "unnecessary, irrelevant and contradictory information that may take away the focus and alter the writer's point of view" (Whittaker 2009, 3).

3) AVOIDING PLAGIARISMS

A writer is expected to have ethical professionalism operating at the highest level. This directly means expressing scientific integrity that attempts to avoid any form of writing that may eventually be termed as Plagiarism (Roig 2006, 1). The word "Plagiarism" is derived from "*plagiare*" in Latin and directly translating to "kidnap" (Das and Panjabi 2011, 67). As described in the coursepack, Plagiarism refers to intentionally failing to give credit to the author of a work or paper where a piece of information was obtained. The information obtained could emanate by direct quoting, paraphrasing, copying and pasting

from internet sources, et cetera. (EUCLID 2019, 5). From my knowledge of academic writing, I have understood it to be a severe academic offense attracting penalties, in most cases, always stated beforehand in many institutions' codes of conduct. From a EUCLID point of view, response papers such as this one are not a "cut and paste" project. The coursepack would be the only go-to source of information. This may lead to Plagiarism and severe academic penalties (EUCLID 2020, 4). Hence, I believe it is essential to conduct adequate research before embarking on each course's task.

The best way to avoid Plagiarism is by employing citations that can come in various forms. The coursepack makes mention of in-text citations and bibliography, which comes at the end of a paper. In-text citations refer to citations found within the write-up and are best used when referencing quotations or paraphrases (EUCLID 2019, 7). Citations are always included in academic papers because it is a common belief that all information within a paper could not have originated from the student's creativity. In other words, there is always definitely a journal or article online or offline that shares the same ideas a student is trying to pass across. In writing this paper, besides from interacting with the provided course pack, I have had to do further research to understand every subject matter best to be discussed. Furthermore, when an idea is perceived as common knowledge, it is advised that its citation be ignored because it is a piece of information that can be found in numerous academic papers (EUCLID 2019, 10)

4) CMS AND TURABIAN STYLE

The Chicago Manual of Style is a style for formatting books and research papers. This is as indicated in the 8th chapter of the coursepack by Dr. Abel Scribe. He further indicates similarities between the CMS and the Turabian style (EUCLID 2019, 44). Kate Turabian developed the Turabian style as a simplified version of the CMS in 1937. It was based on the guidelines found in another book, *A Manual of Style* (Turabian 2007). The CMS crib sheet was divided into Style and Usage, Page Formatting, and End/Footnotes. Being used to the APA style in my previous writing endeavors, I sought to note possible similarities and differences that could be indicated.

Further studies, therefore, made me come across similarities in the styles and usage. For instance, the Latin abbreviations commonly used while writing is to be used in parentheses, or otherwise, should be spelled out in full if used outside parentheses (EUCLID 2019, 44). Another style worthy of mentioning is acronyms and how they are used. They are meant to be first used in parentheses after the full meanings have been expressed. Their next uses, however, can be without parentheses or definition (ibid).

To avoid Plagiarism, it was necessary to note and compare the citation and quotation rules attached to each style. As per EUCLID standard, the Turabian style has it that a citation longer than 2.5 lines should be placed as a block quotation or in a separate paragraph, and without quotation marks (EUCLID 2020, 7). The Chicago Manual indicates that block quotations should be used for quotes having as many words and eight lines. On the other hand, the APA style instructs that a quotation of more than forty words is set aside

in a block away from the main text (EUCLID 2019, 48). I also noted the importance of including the author, year, and page number at the end of every quote.

The CMS takes careful consideration into how pages of books and research papers are to be formatted. The Turabian style takes its cue from this in various aspects of formatting. For example, the standard font to be used is the Times New Roman, with a font size of twelve-points for texts and ten-points for notes (EUCLID 2019, 49). Another essential element in these styles is footnote use to help the reader find a source easily and readily. Footnotes are to be placed at the bottom of the page. They are indicated by a superscript number in the texts and separated from the primary texts by a short rule or separator (EUCLID 2019, 51).

5) LATIN

In the everyday life of the average writer, it has become bound to happen that Latin words or abbreviations are used in any form of writing. As the origin of many English words, Latin has proved to be significant in many academic fields. As a writer, I cannot make do without using any of the standard Latin adaptations (e.g., etc., i.e.). The primary reason why Latin words are existential in English is due to scholars borrowing words. They considered the language to be befitting enough in describing technical terms in technical disciplines such as the sciences (University of Wollongong n.d., 2). Being considered a dead language by some due to it being less spoken and approaching extinction, Latin has been an influential contributor to the English language.

Many Latin abbreviations commonly still in use in academic discourses and every other mode of application. A.M and P.M, for instance, are abbreviations used to signify or determine the time of day in any geographical location. They respectively translate to *ante meridiem* and *post meridiem* (EUCLID 2019, 56-7). In the professional world, the abbreviation CV, derived from *curriculum vitae*, meaning "course of life," is simply an overview of someone's life work and accomplishment. This piece of document is usually requested when a person is looking to get employed by an organization.

Another example is the "et al." commonly used when the authors of a particular source exceed three. The use of the term conforms with EUCLID writing standards (EUCLID 2019, 57). The coursepack includes tables that consisted of adaptable Latin phrases that can always be used in any academic context. However, I understand that the purpose of writing is not just to display facts but also to maintain a level of clarity for the readers. Hence, it is best to write using plain language most simply and directly and avoid unnecessary acronyms and abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56).

6) THE VARIANCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Differentiating between the US and the UK English is an essential ability while writing. However, sticking to a particular variant and maintaining consistency is even more pertinent in writing a correct English text, especially academically (Hansson 2010, 2). The

two variants are particularly more similar than they are different. However, the differences can be identified in the pronunciations of certain words, spellings of some words, and others' meaning (EUCLID 2019, 27-8). The variation in English goes beyond just specific words. The variation can be a result of geography or region. Languages are usually characterized by regional varieties and differences in dialects. I understand this because of how communicating with foreign expatriates in my country has been. Having to deal and communicate with different people from various regions of the world made me realize the extent of variety that the English language possesses.

7) CONCLUSION

The first course, ACA-401D, is the foundation for fulfilling all requirements needed to achieve a doctorate in EUCLID's International Public Health program (DIPH). The course pack and other materials provided (including videos) were vital to me understanding what is required of my writing throughout the program. This course bothers the fact that many instructors care about what their students write and how academically it should be written. The course equally put a worthy test to my writing skills and what I know compared to what will be required by EUCLID standards.

I have realized the vital importance of researching enough research to gather facts and evidence, rock-solid enough to give my work an edge. Plagiarism is explanatory enough to ensure that every source quoted or paraphrased must be duly referenced in the text, as a footnote/endnote, and in the references list. This is equally enhanced with the help of the premium version of Grammarly provided at the start. In addition to this is the EUCLID's checklist for papers and Turabian styles, giving a certain appeal level to the readers.

At this juncture, it is clear that learning and understanding the basics of international academic writing has elevated my writing skills to a certain level, which will only get better. This will be sufficient enough for me to attend to all response papers, essential papers, quizzes, and even the final thesis.

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